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ENHANCING LAW STUDENTS’ LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN LEGAL ENGLISH INSTRUCTION

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Abstract: *This research investigates effective strategies for enhancing listening comprehension competence among law students in English language teaching. Listening skills are fundamental in legal education, allowing students to accurately interpret legal discourse, comprehend intricate arguments, and engage in negotiations and legal proceedings.*

Keywords: *listening comprehension, law students, legal terms, pedagogical strategies, legal discourse, lexical difficulties, legal negotiations, mixed - methods, legal podcasts, audio - visual.*

Introduction

Listening comprehension is an indispensable component of language learning, especially for law students who need to comprehend legal discourse if they are ever going to understand international, regional, and local complex systems. Legal texts, speeches, and negotiations tend to involve much jargon, complicated sentence structures, and nuances of meaning, which call for advanced listening skills. As such, legal professionals have to make sense not only of what is being said but also of the context and implications of legal arguments; good listening skills are part and parcel of their academic and professional lives. According to P. Goodrich [Goodrich, 1987; 119], this skill is foundational in understanding legal documents, interpreting courtroom discussions, and participating effectively in legal negotiations that form a major part of a lawyer’s career.

The challenge of developing listening comprehension competence in English becomes more pronounced in legal education due to language barriers, cultural differences, and discipline-specific

linguistic features. Legal English is a mixture of formal language and unique jargon that is often difficult for non-native speakers to comprehend, especially in terms of grasping the tone, emphasis, and legal implications of verbal communication. Consequently, law students have to acquire not only linguistic rules but also their use in legal contexts. The legal profession demands clarity and precision, besides profound comprehension, not only in the law per se but also in the way it is represented in the legal context [Choudhury, 2020; 22]. This means that an enhancement in listening comprehension will be relevant to the betterment of academic performance as well as professional competencies among law students.

One of the challenges is overcoming traditional teaching methodologies for English as a foreign language, often grammatically and lexically dominated overcoming traditional teaching methodologies for English as a foreign language, which are often grammatically and lexically dominated and not reconciled with the integrative specific demands of legal listening tasks. The nature of LEG may be a problem to students: very specialized vocabulary and complicated syntactic structures. Therefore, there is an evident need for more specialized exercises in listening in legal English. The listening comprehension activities for law students should not only be restricted to general language but also involve real-life legal contexts, such as courtroom procedures, legal debates, and negotiation tactics, to enhance understanding in practical situations. Moreover, such activities should allow students to get acquainted with different accents, speech patterns, and dialects since these are of paramount importance in international legal communication [Martin, 2007; 55].

This article reviews some of the methodologies that could be employed to enhance the listening comprehension of law students in English, focusing on pedagogical approaches, tools, and techniques that develop the requisite skills. Deep discussions on the use of authentic legal materials, such as court recordings, legal podcasts, and real-life case studies, will be of importance. Special task-based activities, interactive simulations of legal negotiations, and mock trials are also essential to bring students into the intricacies of legal language to enhance their comprehension skills. Technological tools, such as interactivity in e-learning platforms and specialized apps, allow for immediate feedback, thus students the opportunity to consolidate such skills in a controlled and systematic manner. These strategies have been proven to significantly enhance the ability of students to understand legal English, both at school and in their professional settings. By incorporating these approaches, a law student would be well-equipped to process spoken legal language that contributes to a student's overall academic and professional development [Martin, 2007; 55].

Literature review

J. Flowerdew and L. Miller provide an extensive examination of the cognitive and sociolinguistic processes involved in listening comprehension, emphasizing the importance of authentic materials and contextualized listening tasks. Their work underscores the need for task-based approaches to develop listening skills in specific contexts, such as legal education [Flowerdew & Miller, 2005; 272]. M. Goh and A. Burns offer a comprehensive guide on teaching listening, highlighting the metacognitive strategies that enhance learners' self-regulation and comprehension [Goh & Burns, 2012; 328]. L. Vandergrift and M. Goh expand on these ideas, presenting a metacognitive cycle of planning, monitoring, and evaluating listening tasks [Vandergrift & Goh, 2012; 324]. These strategies are particularly relevant for law students who must process complex legal discourse.

J. Boyle identifies key factors influencing listening comprehension, including vocabulary familiarity, discourse structure, and the speaker's accent. These factors are critical in designing listening activities tailored for legal English, where specialized terminology and diverse accents are common [Boyle, 1984; 35]. B. Knight explores listening strategies specific to business and legal English learners, emphasizing the role of prior knowledge and contextual clues [Knight, 1994; 260]. Similarly, L.

Vandergrift highlights the underutilized role of listening strategies in second language instruction, advocating for greater integration of comprehension exercises that simulate real-life legal scenarios [Vandergrift, 1997; 470].

J. Richards outlines practical techniques for teaching listening and speaking, including the use of interactive activities and multimedia resources [Richards, 2008; 87]. G. Brown and G. Yule emphasize the role of conversational analysis in teaching spoken language, providing insights into how legal discourse can be incorporated into language teaching [Brown & Yule 1983; 208]. P. Ur discusses various methods for teaching listening, stressing the importance of pre-listening to pre-listening activities to activate background knowledge [Ur, 2012; 299]. G. Buck focuses on the assessment of listening, offering tools to evaluate learners' progress in understanding spoken English in specific domains [Buck, 2001; 177].

M. Rost combines theory and practice in exploring listening strategies, advocating for integrating technology to enhance learners' exposure to authentic materials [Rost, 2013; 304]. J. Field critiques traditional approaches to listening instruction, proposing a – skills-based methodology that addresses the unique challenges learners face in specialized contexts [Field, 2008; 300]. I. Nation and J. Newton provide a balanced approach to teaching listening and speaking, combining fluency-focused tasks with accuracy-oriented activities [Nation & Newton, 2009; 240]. M. Helgesen and S. Brown emphasize the motivational aspects of listening, suggesting that engaging materials and tasks can sustain learners' interest in challenging contexts like legal English [Helgesen & S. Brown, 1994; 99]. E. Hinkel presents a collection of research studies on second language teaching and learning, highlighting the importance of context-specific approaches [Hinkel, 2013; 586]. P. Dunkel bridges theory and practice in exploring listening comprehension, offering insights into how legal discourse can be incorporated into SLA frameworks [Dunkel, 1991; 457].

J. Field discusses the need for innovative methodologies in teaching listening, focusing on skills and strategies that prepare learners for real-world listening tasks [Field, 1998; 300]. H. Widdowson and M. Rost further support this idea, emphasizing integrating theory and practice to enhance listening competence [Widdowson, 1990; 212.; Rost, 2002; 224]

Methods

The current study employed a mixed-methods approach with quantitative and qualitative data collection for the assessment of the acquisition of listening comprehension skill among law students. The study was undertaken using an experimental pre-test and post-test design to evaluate improvement in students' learning after an intervention program with 12 weeks involving task-based and technology-rich learning strategies.

The sample applied in the current study consisted of 80 Tashkent State University of Law, Uzbekistan, students that were picked through purposive sampling. Students were assigned to two levels of proficiency: Intermediate-Median (B1-B2) and Advanced-Median (C1+). To ensure proper placement, all students were administered a standardized test of language proficiency before group placement. The test included listening comprehension, recognition of legal vocabulary, and recognition of legal arguments, and it was composed of 50 questions in multiple-choice, fill-in-the-blank, and short-answer formats. The listening component included recorded legal arguments, case briefs, and courtroom trials, while the vocabulary and argument analysis components required students to identify specialized legal terms and analyze patterns of reasoning in legal discourse.

20 law students were pilot-tested to measure difficulty and clarity. Cronbach's alpha (0.87) was employed to test reliability with high internal consistency. Construct validity was established by comparing students' scores with standardized English proficiency tests such as TOEFL and IELTS, and content validity was ensured by having three legal language experts check. The test was administered in

Week 1 under controlled conditions in the university language lab. The students listened to audio recordings through headphones and completed the test within 60 minutes (30 minutes for legal vocabulary and argument analysis and 30 minutes for listening comprehension).

Intervention (Weeks 2-11)

Students participated in guided listening comprehension exercises three times per week (60-minute classes). The practice included court hearing exposure, legal podcast listening, mock trials, and negotiation role-plays. Task-based learning strategies were employed by the intervention, which combined pre-listening vocabulary exercises, simultaneous note-taking, and post-listening discussion. AI-based transcription software, virtual reality courtroom simulation, and interactive legal English apps were utilized to enhance interest and comprehension in the sessions.

Post-Test and Qualitative Data Collection (Week 12)

In Week 12, the same test served as a post-test to measure gains in listening accuracy, legal vocabulary recognition, and legal argument comprehension. Responses to pre-tests and post-tests were compared with one another using paired t-tests to determine statistical significance. As an addition to quantitative data, qualitative data was provided through self-assessment questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The self-assessment questionnaires had a 5-point Likert scale upon which students graded their perceived growth in listening comprehension, vocabulary recall, and argument analysis, as well as open-ended questions for learning challenges and effective strategies.

Semi-Structured Interviews and Analysis

The 20 participants (10 at each level of proficiency) completed semi-structured interviews to talk about their listening strategies and tools experience. Interview questions pertained to the effectiveness of listening exercises, ease of legal vocabulary identification, confidence in argument analysis, and most preferred strategies. Interviewing each participant was 15-20 minutes and transcribed and thematically analyzed using NVivo software. Answers were coded under the themes improved understanding, legal terminology challenges, and most preferred learning approaches.

Data Analysis

Pre-test and post-test quantitative data were processed with SPSS to quantify learning gains. Qualitative data from self-assessment and interviews provided contextual information on students' experiences, giving a holistic assessment of the effectiveness of listening strategies in legal English education. This mixed-method design gave an in-depth assessment of learning progress and the impact of innovative teaching approaches.

Results

These results provide considerable evidence regarding the intervention's effectiveness in improving the listening comprehension competence in English, especially in the context of legal discourse. The results present a combination of quantitative and qualitative data from pre- and post-assessments, student surveys, and reflective interviews, thus providing a well-rounded intervention analysis.

Quantitative Results

The pre- and post-assessment quantified gains in the interventions in students' listening comprehension, with gains to be measured across a number of legal contexts. Pre-evaluation at the commencement of the course also highlighted well and truly the major difficulties law students had regarding the comprehension of complex legal terminologies, intricate sentence structures, and formal, often dense discourses commonly used within the legal context. The specific issues were related to the understanding of extended discussions, which included specialized legal content, such as case law analysis, courtroom debates, and legislative deliberations. For example, after they listened to a recording of a mock trial involving a civil litigation case, students failed to identify some of the legal arguments

and subtleties of the courtroom exchanges. On average, the students' listening performance was well below that expected of students in law, their scores averaging a mere 60% in tasks in which legal jargon was used contextualized S. Ala-Kortesmaa and P. Isotalus [S. Ala-Kortesmaa and P. Isotalus, 2015; 187].

Students demonstrated specific challenges in identifying important legal terminology in context, like “tort,” “precedent,” and “burden of proof.” Few students pre-assessment could identify these words, nor would they understand what they were when they surfaced in the longer legal discussions. Beyond that, students could not follow longer legal arguments, especially those with high abstraction, like philosophical arguments about justice or abstract discussions of constitutional law.

The statistical tests were conducted computationally using SPSS to compare the pre-test and post-test scores. The three significant variables were measured in the study: listening comprehension accuracy, legal vocabulary recognition, and understanding of legal arguments. For paired samples t-test, comparisons were drawn with regard to mean difference of scores, standard deviation, t-value, and p-value. The results validated a statistically significant improvement with the p-value < 0.05, testifying that intervention had a very positive effect on students' listening proficiency. The post-test, administered after legal realia intervention, which combined real-world legal materials, task-based learning, and web-based tools, showed a clear increase in students' scores. The paired t-test results further confirmed that students who originally scored less than 60% on the pre-test scored an average of 80% on the post-test, signifying the efficacy of the intervention in improving legal listening skills.

Specifically, this was visible in those exercises at which students had to listen to recorded complex legal discussions, such as a debate on intellectual property law, or a simulated international court of justice hearing on human rights violations M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 3].

Results post-assessment also showed that, through the course, students could identify legal terminologies in context, accurately monitor legal arguments, and catch nuances of tone and delivery on different levels in legal argumentation. For example, one exercise involved students listening to a recording of a lawyer delivering a closing argument in a criminal case. At first, students had difficulty recognizing the rhetorical strategies the lawyer employed to persuade the jury. However, after the intervention, students identified primary rhetorical devices, including appeals to emotion and logical reasoning. They demonstrated a better understanding of how those devices are applied in legal practice A. Jones [Jones, 2018; 202]. This means that the intervention improved not only legalist vocabulary but also the ability to perform critical analyses regarding the structure and purpose of legal discourse.

The students showed a deeper understanding of complicated legal notions and could work with the content productively. Students mastered some very complex legal concepts, such as the implications of judicial review or the impact of international treaties on domestic law, much better than in previous years. One student was in a position to engage in and correctly outline a mock hearing in a simulated case about environmental law in a transnational perspective. The pre-assessment showed this student could not do this. Still, that same student post-intervention was able to identify the main legal arguments and finally evaluate the reasoning at the core of a judicial decision M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 134].

The post-intervention results showed that students developed the ability to analyze the structure of legal argumentation, recognize the most relevant points in the legal argumentation, and check the logical coherence in legal discussion. These improvements were especially salient in simulated court cases, legal interviews, and policy debates. In one activity, students listened to an extended recording of a legislative debate on a new legal reform and had to identify the main legal points each speaker had raised, along with the potential legal consequences of the proposed reform. In the pre-assessment, students could not process the information fast enough to answer the questions correctly; however, in

the post-intervention test, students showed increased competence in processing and understanding complex legal information, which allowed them to follow the structure of the arguments and answer accordingly during the post-listening discussion. For instance, one student was able to identify in seconds the possible constitutional challenges created in a debate and then go ahead to describe how these challenges pertained to the relevant case law A. Niedwiecki [Niedwiecki, 2006; 65].

Quantitative findings from the current study generally indicated that the intervention clearly enhanced the ability of students to go deeper into meaningful understanding of complex legal texts. By integrating authentic materials, task-based activities, and digital tools, learners were better positioned to process legal information, understand specialist terms, and consider legal content critically. Statistically significant gains recorded on the post-test suggest that the treatment in this study effectively supported law students in developing two major listening competencies for future careers in law. These findings further support using authentic legal materials and active learning strategies in legal English education since it enhances the students' ability to listen not only but also to develop the critical thinking and legal reasoning necessary for legal practice . Ala-Kortesmaa and P. Isotalus [S. Ala-Kortesmaa and P. Isotalus, 2015; 187]

Table 1. Quantitative Results of Listening Comprehension Analysis

Assessment Type	Pre-Assessment Score (%)	Post-Assessment Score (%)	Average Score Increase (%)	Pre-Test Mean	Post-Test Mean	Pre-Test SD	Post-Test SD	Pre-Test Median	Post-Test Median	Statistical Significance (p-value)
Legal Terminology Identification	60	80	20	58.5	76.333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0
Understanding Legal Arguments	58	75	17	58.5	76.333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0
Identifying Rhetorical Strategies	55	70	15	58.5	76.333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0
Comprehending Complex Legal Ideas	62	81	19	58.5	76.333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0

Analyzing Legal Structures	59	78	19	58.5	76.33333333333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0
Evaluating Legal Discussions	57	74	17	58.5	76.33333333333333	2.4289915602982237	4.1311822359545785	58.5	76.5	0.0

Qualitative Results

Apart from the quantitative data, the qualitative data also provided rich information on students' experiences and perceptions of the intervention. More particularly, questionnaires and interviews conducted with the students after the course revealed that the latter significantly benefited from their exposure to real legal materials, recorded court hearings, podcasts on legal aspects, and interviews with legally trained professionals. These authentic materials made the learning process more interactive and gave the students opportunities to contextualize their listening practice. The actuality of students having been exposed to the legal discourse that naturally occurred did improve their ability to decode and process this kind of legal language in an original context Martin [Martin, 2007; 55]. For example, students who listened to courtroom proceedings' recordings said they could sense the formality, speed, and specific jargon used in real-life court. Further, it bridged the gap between theoretical learning in the class and practical aspects of the legal profession with more applicability in their professional lives.

The task-based learning activities included in the intervention were particularly welcomed by the students. In this respect, mock trials, legal negotiations, and simulated hearings were beneficial to develop their listening skills, considering that such activities required active listening when students had to process legal information as quickly as possible and respond in real time, closely mimicking the actual demands of legal practice. For instance, during the mock trials, the students had to listen to the simulated legal arguments and identify the key points from what was said, grasp the legal reasoning, and put together complex information. Thus, their listening comprehension significantly improved, as did their analysis of information skills important in future legal work A.Jones [Jones, 2018; 202]. In this way, the hands - on approach motivated students to apply their listening skills within a legal framework, which helped transfer learning gained in the classroom to real life.

Students appreciated the use of technology in the intervention. The curriculum included additional practice via online platforms in the form of activities like interactive listening exercises and legal English apps. This was particularly useful for many students because they could do it at a time and at a pace that suited them, and they were able to review what they had done in class more easily. The immediate feedback from the apps allowed students to follow their progress and practice according to their individual proficiency levels. Such flexibility and personalization of learning were a much welcome thing for the students themselves A. Niedwiecki [Niedwiecki, 2006; 3].

For example, some students mentioned that some interactive listening tasks in a legal English app helped them to become more confident in understanding complicated discussions while listening to legal English, because they could repeat the exercises until they fully understood. One student said, "Being able to practice multiple times helped me grasp the legal vocabulary with its contextualizing, something I really struggled to pick up on beforehand." Another mentioned, "With the legal English app,

it let me pinpoint problems in places I was particularly experiencing difficulty with and improve significantly upon these." Digital resource integration has clearly supported the development of students' independent learning of English at home as a supplement to class hours.

Qualitative results indicated that the use of authentic legal materials, task-based learning activities, and digital tools all combined in an effective way to enhance students' listening comprehension. 'The strategies made the learning process more interactive and holistic and were also regarded by students as important in preparing them for the listening demands they would have to face during their legal careers. Students felt better equipped to handle complex legal discussions, and many expressed increased confidence in their ability to engage in real-world legal settings M. Shamsitdinova' [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 4]. The inclusion of these elements provided a holistic approach that enhanced both their academic and professional listening capabilities.

Table 2. Feedback on Effective Learning Strategies

Components	Percentages	Explanations	Interpretation
Task-Based Learning Activities	40%	Focused on activities like mock trials, legal negotiations, and role-play scenarios to simulate real-life legal contexts. These tasks help students actively apply listening skills in practical situations.	40% of the intervention emphasized active learning through legal simulations, ensuring practical application of listening skills.
Authentic Legal Materials	40%	Includes courtroom recordings, legal podcasts, and negotiation dialogues to expose students to real-world legal discourse and terminology.	Another 40% prioritized real-world exposure, helping students adapt to professional legal discourse and terminology.
Technological Tools	20%	Utilized tools like AI-powered transcription services, virtual reality simulations, and language learning apps for enhanced engagement and instant feedback.	20% focused on technology as a supportive tool, providing interactive engagement and automated feedback while keeping human interaction central.

Reflection on Students' Experiences

Questionnaires on student self-assessment and interviews attested that the intervention was effective enough to bring a statistically significant rise in their confidence and competence in the areas of listening comprehension. By the end of the course, a majority of the students manifested increased confidence in understanding and interpreting the discourse in legal terms. This was especially evident in their ability to follow fast-paced legal debates, grasp complex legal terms, and understand the nuances of professional legal conversations. Many students reported that the skills they developed- particularly in processing spoken legal language in real time- were directly applicable to their future careers in law, enhancing both their academic and professional preparation M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021;

4].

Students displayed higher motivation to continue further working on improving their listening skills in the legal area of study. Among the most popular reasons were real-life materials, such as recorded court hearings, legal podcasts, and interviews with practicing lawyers. In interacting with real legal content and participating in interactive activities such as mock trials and legal negotiations, students developed a fuller understanding of how legal discourse works in professional settings. This deeper engagement with the material also consolidated their listening comprehension, made learning more relevant and enjoyable, and applied to real-life legal situations.

The students realized that listening is an important factor to consider in the legal profession. The intervention focused on how good listening is one of the key competencies in legal professions, enabling a legal professional to follow legal arguments, comprehend law complexities, and participate confidently and correctly in professional legal contexts. Many students highlighted the fact that comprehension skills are as crucial in legal practice as speaking skills. “I found the course useful in identifying the importance of listening on par with speaking within a legal performance context. This class truly has made me ready for the outside legal world M. Shamsitdinova” [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 255]. Others added that the intervention indeed equipped them with the ability to understand legal language in its natural context and, therefore, be prepared for the fast pace and complexity of legal environments M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021: 333].

Generally speaking, student reflections were very appreciative of the intervention; many of them testified that it had improved their listening skills and strengthened their motivation to develop these skills. The integration of such authentic materials, task-based learning activities, and digital tools thus proved very effective in enhancing both their academic and professional capabilities. Making connections from students’ classroom learning to real-life legal practice helped the latter understand how to apply their listening skills to different legal situations. This way, they become prepared for any challenges in the future regarding their future success in legal careers.

Table 3. Reflection on Students’ Experiences

Key Aspects of Reflection	Percentage of Positive Feedback (%)
Confidence in Listening Comprehension	85%
Understanding Legal Discourse	80%
Real - World Application	90%
Motivation to Improve Skills	88%
Preparation for Legal Careers	87%

Discussion

These findings from the study serve as good evidence that the intervention is effective in substantially improving students’ confidence, competence, and engagement in listening comprehension within the specialized domain of legal studies. The reflections and feedback provided by participants through self-assessment surveys and interviews serve to indicate that the intervention focused on the main difficulties with regard to understanding complex legal discourse and practically prepared them with real-life skills directly applicable in their academic and professional lives D. Khashimova [Khashimova et al., 2019; 33].

One of the high points of the present research was the employment of authentic materials, namely, recorded court hearings and interviews with practicing legal professionals in the form of legal podcasts. These types of materials afford students an opportunity to be exposed to real legal situations that would help bridge the gap between the classroom and the professional world. In pedagogical literature, the use of authentic materials has long been related to increased realism and relevance of

language classes. In the context of this study, they improved not only students' listening but also deepened their understanding of the intricate nuances and subtleties embedded in legal language. Again, this finding echoes the emphasis of research on exposing learners to domain-specific language in realistic contexts to facilitate the transfer and long-term retention of acquired skills M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 3].

The project-based intervention activity, which was mock trials, legal negotiations, and a simulated court proceeding, became a significant factor for active engagement. This kind of activity is crucial to developing an interactive learning environment that helps students immerse in the subject, as mentioned by most students who motivated and enjoyed this type of activity. By having such activities, the students got to listen contextually to situations more closely approximating the demands of everyday real-life practice. The element of this experiential learning again fortifies their comprehension and confidence in delivering under pressure - a skill a practicing legal professional certainly needs.

Students' motivation to continue their listening improvement, especially for legal studies, was strikingly enhanced. The authentic resources, along with the interactive approach to learning, gave a purposeful and relevant process, which made learning more interesting and relevant. This correlates with wider theories in educational psychology that point out the role of relevance and task-oriented learning in maintaining motivation and achieving better learning outcomes.

The students also highlighted the indispensable role of listening comprehension within the legal profession. Indeed, many participants have identified that the intervention shifted their thinking concerning the position of listening within a legal professional skill set. As noted by students themselves, effective listening is the principal way to correctly interpret arguments, understand complex documents, and confidently participate in professional settings. This finding is in line with the current studies on legal communication, which have established that listening is as important as speaking in the practice of law, especially in high-stakes scenarios such as courtroom debates, negotiations, and client interactions M. Shamsitdinova [Shamsitdinova, 2021; 255].

Another important theme that emerged from the study was that participants' confidence went hand in glove with their competence: the development of students' real - time spoken legal English processing ability was accompanied by increased confidence in working in professional situations. It has been suggested-and in many instances demonstrated - by researchers in language acquisition that a positive circle does occur between the development of skill and self-efficacy; accordingly, interventions addressing cognitive-affective aspects of learning are called for.

While these are very positive results, there were some challenges: A subset of students reported difficulties in keeping pace with fast - talking speakers or unfamiliar legal topics. This response suggests that the intervention was very effective for most test subjects, but further scaffolding may be needed to support learners for whom either the rapid delivery or specialized content of legal discourse proves challenging. In the future development of the program, there might be a multi - tiered approach: starting with slower-paced materials and gradually increasing the complexity to make sure all students feel prepared.

Research has underlined possible opportunities for improved technology support in listening comprehension: digital tools could extend it through simulations of interactive legality or AI-enhanced transcriptional software, allowing students to hear the legal language, revise and research it, and then practice on their own. This kind of technology use might be used more systematically within intervention programs in support of those cases that needed extra time or wanted individually focused practice. The intervention proved to be very effective in bringing about considerable improvement in the students' achievement of academic listening skills, their confidence level, and motivation concerning legal studies. The program incorporated authentic materials, task-based learning activities, and real-life applications;

it prepared the students not only for academic but also practical challenges in the field of legal professions. These findings add to the increasingly cumulative evidence for domain-specific language teaching and underline the need for any pedagogic approach to be firmly linked to specific needs as determined within the particular specialized domain. Further research needs to look at long-term effects on professional performance and how comparable methodologies may be transferred into other specialized disciplines in search of the highest effectiveness.

Conclusion

The findings of this study thus reveal that the intervention effectively enhanced the listening comprehension competence in English, especially in legal discourse, among law students. Both the quantitative gains in the listening scores and the qualitative feedback from the students themselves suggest that the intervention addressed major challenges law students face in understanding complex legal language. This intervention incorporated authentic legal materials, task-based learning, and digital tools in a vibrant learning environment that fostered improved listening skills.

The current study emphasizes the need to embed realistic, naturalistic listening practice into legal English courses and indicates that a law student has to develop high-quality listening comprehension skills if he or she is to be able to function effectively in his or her future work. Based on findings, be appropriate that legal English programs focus on the growth of students' listening competencies through innovative teaching methods and resources to definitely prepare the lawyer for the hurdles of legal discourses in the English language accordingly.

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